

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SEISMIC DESIGN CRITERIA FOR A 15-STORIED BUILDING UNDER IS CODE 1893 (PART 1): 2016 AND NEPAL BUILDING CODE NBC 105:2020

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Abstract

Nepal is the country which lies in the seismically active region. Nepal has long history regarding high intensity earthquake. Nepal publish first Seismic code NBC 105 in year 1994 AD. Due to the same topographical condition in Nepal and India, Nepal's designer adopted IS code standard for seismic analysis. Again new version of NBC 105 was published in 2020 AD. But till date IS 456-2000 is used and adopted as design code in Nepal. Total 4 sample Including 2 rectangular and 2 L-shaped building of 15 storied building was taken into account to find out displacement, base shear, peak ground acceleration, drift. However due to higher load factor and critical load combination IS code shows higher reinforcement then NBC. The purpose of research is to examine multi- storied building utilizing the latest version of NBC 105:2020 and IS 2016.

Keywords: High Rise building IS code 1983, Nepal building code NBC code 105:2020, seismic design criteria.

I. INTRODUCTION

Before the publication of NBC the structural design of RC building in Nepal used to be done by referring to Indian Standard code. As we know that Nepal and India are neighboring countries and Northern part of India and Nepal weather, geology, topography are similar so following Indian building design code for designing building. Still Indian standard code is adopted in Nepal. After introduction of NBC 1994 AD and the massive earthquake in 2015 AD, Nepal's government again publishes the new NBC code for earthquake design. Likewise Indian Government also publishes new code IS 1983: 2016. Only earthquake code is different but the design code for structure adopted in Nepal is Indian standard code. Nepalese code needs sufficient information to address current design measure. The main aim of the thesis is for comparing building design with Nepal Building code and Indian Building code. The building of 15 storied is taken for comparative analysis on static and dynamic behavior of the building.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main aim of the purpose is to examine multi-storied RC building using static and dynamic analysis using the latest version of NBC-105 : 2020 and IS 1983(part 1): 2020. The objective of the study that research aim to accomplish is:

- 1) By using the Etabs, to generate model of 15 storied for static and dynamic loading condition and to analysis the model contrasting the value.
- 2) To compare and find out the difference of different seismic parameter like storey drift, displacement, base shear, peak ground acceleration using both the code.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Shrestha, J.K., Paudel, N., Koirala, B., & Giri, B.R. (2021) [1]. There was the significant impact due to Gorkha Earthquake in 2015 on building due to which there was a recognized need for updated regulations to

ensure the safety and structural integrity of buildings for its design and construction practices in Nepal. The study utilizes both linear and non-linear static analysis, as well as linear dynamic analysis, to assess the performance of low-rise reinforced concrete buildings. This comprehensive approach allows for a thorough evaluation of how different codes impact structural behavior under seismic loads

Banjara, R., Thapa, D., & Katuwal, T.B. (2021). [2] The construction of reinforced concrete (RC) buildings has been a prevalent practice for many decades, where was some limitations of traditional unreinforced masonry. The latter often fails to meet the necessary requirement along with integrity and ductility criteria required for safety, especially in seismic regions. There is the study on focusing on different reinforced concrete (RC) building analyzing between Nepal National Building Code and indian standard (IS) codes. There was focus on both previously existing and revised standards using various response parameters through different approaches, including linear and non-linear static and linear dynamic methods.

Adhikari, B., & Poudel, A. (2023). [3]The study analyzes two types of building models: a 2-storey and a 3-storey structure. These models are essential for understanding how different building heights respond to seismic forces under the two codes involves conducting an equivalent static analysis for the seismic evaluation of the building models.

Sah, K.K. (2020). [4].Focusing on the differences between the old IS 1893-2002 and the new IS 1893-2016 code incorporates more realistic assumptions about the behavior of concrete structures, such as using cracked section properties for analysis, which is crucial for accurate seismic performance assessments.

Prateek Raj Pandit 2019. [7]The analysis mainly focus on storey drift, lateral sway, base shear[3].The study focused on a G+21 reinforced concrete (RC) frame building. Analysis was conducted on the seismic response of buildings underlying different soil type. The researchers utilized ETABS 2016 for the analysis and design of the building models for structural analysis, particularly for buildings, enabling detailed simulations of seismic behavior. The analysis mainly focus on base shear, displacement, design reinforced quality.

P Pokhrel, R Rathore Oct. 2022 . [10]The study involves two 10-storey buildings, each designed with a regular plan. Both buildings consist of three bays in each direction using ETABS, a widely used software for structural analysis and design. Research include both static and dynamic analysis methods focusing on key parameters such as displacement, storey drift, storey shear, overturning moment, stiffness, base shear, time period, and forces in columns.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Here, 15 storied building is taken into analysis. There are 2 types of building related to shape, one rectangular and other is L shaped building. Different four (4) model are prepared to study the building related with NBC and IS.

For both the model

Rectangular and L-Shaped building with static and dynamic analysis using NBC 105: 2020 and IS code 1983 (part1)2016.

1. Loads For both Rectangular and L-Shaped building

Brick Masonary: Unit Weight 20 KN/m³

Finishes (Floor Finishes) :1.5 KN/m²

Reinforced Concrete Elements: Unit Weight 25 KN/m³

Live Load: 3 KN/m²

Roof live : 0.75 KN/m²

2. Lateral Load : Earthquake loads as per NBC: 105:2020 and IS code 1983 (part1)2016

Zone factor (Z) = 0.3 and 0.24 as per NBC and IS code respectively.

Importance factor : 1.25 and 1.2 as per NBC and IS code respectively

Response reduction factor : 5 for IS code.

Soil type : C and II as per NBC and IS code respectively.

3. Load combination as per NBC 105 and IS 1983 for both Rectangular and L-Shaped building.

Load Combination considered in the analysis are mentioned below:

For static consideration as per NBC 105

1.2 Dead Load+1.5Live Load

Dead Load +0.3Live Load+EQX(Service limit State)

Dead Load +0.3Live Load -EQX(Service limit State)

Dead Load+0.3Live Load +EQY(Service limit State)

Dead Load+0.3Live Load -EQY(Service limit State)

Dead Load+0.3Live Load+EQX(Ultimate Limit State)

Dead Load+0.3Live Load-EQX(Ultimate Limit State)

Dead Load+0.3Live Load+EQY(Ultimate Limit State)

Dead Load +0.3Live Load-EQY(Ultimate Limit State)

For dynamic analysis

All Load combination including static and provided

Dead Load +0.3Live Load+RSX

Dead Load +0.3Live Load+RSY

Dead Load +0.3Live Load-RSX

Dead Load +0.3Live Load-RSY

Load Combination considered in the analysis are mentioned

below: For static consideration as per IS 1893

1.5Dead Load

1.5(Dead Load+Live Load)

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load+EQX)

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load-EQX)

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load+EQY)

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load-EQY)

1.5(Dead Load+EQX)

1.5(Dead Load-EQX)

1.5(Dead Load+EQY)

1.5(Dead Load-EQY)

0.9Dead Load+1.5EQX

0.9Dead Load-1.5EQX

0.9Dead Load+1.5EQY

0.9Dead Load-1.5EQY

For dynamic analysis

All Load combination including static and provided

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load+RSX)

1.2(Dead Load+Live Load+RSY)

1.5(Dead Load+RSX)

1.5(Dead Load+RSY)

0.9Dead Load+1.5RSX

0.9Dead Load+1.5RSY

4. Material Properties for both building

- Grade of concrete: M35 for beam, Slab and Column
- Grade of steel : Fe 500
- Modulus of Elasticity of concrete (E_c): $5000\sqrt{f_{ck}}$ N/mm²
- Modulus of Elasticity of Steel (E_s): 2×10^5 N/mm²

5. Element for both building

Following are the element dimension considered in the building for analysis:

Slab = 150 mm

Wall thickness exterior = 230 mm

Interior wall thickness= 115mm

Size of column= 800 mm X 800 mm

Size of beam= 200mm x 500mm and 350X 500 for NBC and IS respectively.

Size of secondary beam= 230X 350 mm

Shear wall thickness : 200mm and 230 as per NBC and IS respectively.

6. Size

Size of the building Rectangular

Area: 720 sq. m

Height of building : 52.5 m

Storied of building : 15

Size of the L-Shaped building

Area: 480 sq. m

Height of building : 52.5 m

Storied of building : 15

Model Generated in Etsbs

Fig.1 Model of 15 storied Rectangular Building

Fig.2 L-shaped 15 storied building model

Fig.3. Rectangular model with finishing load

Fig.4 L-shaped model with floor finish

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. DISPLACEMENTS:

Table 1 and 2 shows the displacement of the building in X-direction and y-direction. The value find using NBC is higher than the of IS code. There is about 49.105% more displacement in rectangular building design by NBC than that of IS code provided by EQXULS. Also there is about 46.04% more displacement in L-shaped building design by NBC than that of IS code provided by RSX.

TABLE 1 Displacement for rectangular building

For rectangular building			
	Maximum displacement in NBC	Maximum displacement in IS	Percentage
EQX ULS	159.198	81.023	49.1055164
EQX SLS	127.358	N/A	N/A
RSX	121.643	63.029	48.18526343
EQY ULS	144.196	75.275	47.79674887
EQY SLS	115.357	N/A	N/A
RSY	117.301	62.096	47.06268489

TABLE 2 : Displacement for L-shape building.

For L-shaped building			
	Maximum displacement in NBC	Maximum displacement in IS	Percentage
EQX ULS	127.901	72.176	43.56885404
EQX SLS	102.32	N/A	N/A
RSX	107.209	57.848	46.0418435
EQY ULS	115.037	75.196	34.63320497
EQY SLS	92.029	N/A	N/A
RSY	110.602	67.61	38.87090649

2. Drift :

Table 3 and 4 shows the drift of the building in X-direction and y-direction. The value find using NBC is higher than the of IS code. There is about 48.52 % more drift in rectangular building design by NBC than that of IS code provided by EQXULS. Also there is about 46.36% more drift in L-shaped building design by NBC than that of IS code provided by RSX.

TABLE 3: Drift for Rectangular building.

For rectangular building			
	Maximum drift according to NBC	Maximum drift according to IS	percentage
EQX ULS	0.00374	0.001925143	48.52559206
EQX SLS	0.002992	N/A	N/A
RSX	0.002758857	0.001463143	46.96561723
EQY ULS	0.003394571	0.001790857	47.24349802
EQY SLS	0.002715714	N/A	N/A
RSY	0.002702	0.001438	46.78016284

TABLE 4: Drift for L-Shape building.

For L-shape building			
	Maximum drift according to NBC	Maximum drift according to IS	percentage
EQX ULS	0.003020857	0.001703429	43.61108484
EQX SLS	0.002416857	N/A	N/A
RSX	0.002480571	0.001330571	46.36028565
EQY ULS	0.002736571	0.001779429	34.97598664
EQY SLS	0.002189429	N/A	N/A
RSY	0.002632857	0.001561714	40.68366793

3. Base shear

Table 5 shows the base shear for different shape of building extracted from two different code. The value of base shear obtained from NBC is high than that of IS code for both of the rectangular and L-shape building.

TABLE 5: Base shear for different building

Model	Base shear in KN	
	EQX ULS	EQY ULS
Rectangular buidling (NBC)	-8119.4099	-8119.4099
Rectangular buidling (IS)	-7191.3651	-7191.3651
L-shape Building(NBC)	-5243.1711	-5243.1711
L-shape Building(IS)	-4825.0544	-4825.0544

4. Peak floor Acceleration

Table 6 shows the Peak ground acceleration for different shape of building extracted from two different codes. The value of Peak ground acceleration obtained from NBC is high than that of IS code for both of the rectangular and L-shape building.

TABLE 6: Peak ground acceleration for different building

peak ground acceleration m/sec ²				
	NBC 15 storied Rectangular	IS 15 storied Rectangular	NBC 15 storied L shape	IS 15 storied L shape
RSX	1.97132	1.60907	1.79758	1.66707
RSY	1.88385	1.69296	1.89642	1.80149

VI. CONCLUSIONS

After analyzing the building with two different codes we get the following conclusion:

- The displacement of 15 storied building analyzed using NBC and IS code, NBC shows more displacement than IS code NBC for both types of building.
- The drift of 15 storied building analyzed using NBC and IS code; NBC shows more drift than IS code NBC for both types of building.
- The peak ground acceleration of 15 storied building analyzed using NBC and IS code; NBC shows more value of peak ground acceleration than IS code NBC for both types of building.
- Size used in 15 storied building to be structurally safe, size consider to be high using IS code than that of NBC for both types of building.
- Rebar abstracted from IS code shows higher value than that of NBC for both types of building due to higher load factor and critical load combination.

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